

LEARNING ENVIRONMENT IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF LEARNERS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 32

Issue 2

Pages: 196-208

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3054

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14861954

Manuscript Accepted: 01-27-2025

Learning Environment in Relation to Academic Performance of Learners

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the relationship between the learning environment and academic performance of learners of the two (2) extension schools in District IV, Division of Bago City in relation to selected variables such as facilities, painting and lighting, proper ventilation of classroom, seats and arrangement, chalkboard, teachers' behavior, students' behavior, and student-teacher relationship for S.Y. 2023-2024. An adapted and revised questionnaire made by Irene Pajarillo-Aquino, (2019) Cagayan State University Andrews Campus, in her study about the Classroom Environment and Its Effects on the Students' Academic Performance of the College of Teacher Education was administered to 148 key stage 2 respondents of the study. A descriptive-correlational research design was used in this study. In determining the learning environment and the level of academic performance of the learners, mean was used. In terms of the relationship between academic performance and the aforementioned variables, gamma coefficient was used. A quantitative study of two extension schools in District IV, Bago City (S.Y. 2023-2024) obtained a very good learning environment and high academic performance. However, regression analysis revealed that there was no significant relationship between the learning environment and the academic performance of key stage 2 learners. It was recommended that the Department of Education provide enough resources in all schools, particularly those in remote areas with only partitioned classrooms, to ensure an appropriate environment for the teaching and learning process, resulting in quality graduates, as well as that the schools promote harmonious relationships not only for learners but also with their parents and other stakeholders.

Keywords: *academic performance, key stage 2 learners, learning environment, student's behavior, student-teacher relationship, teachers' behavior*

Introduction

The learning environment is important in molding academic success because it includes the physical, social, and psychological circumstances in which learning takes place (Hattie, 2018). Research consistently demonstrates that a well-designed learning environment enhances academic achievements, while an unappealing setting can hinder academic growth (Weinstein & Worrell, 2018).

Some of the schools are impacted by environmental factors, such as the partitioning of classrooms, the absence of school buildings, the absence of adequate ventilation and lighting, and the lack of sufficient space for the teaching-learning process. These factors, in turn, will have an impact on the academic performance of the students. Poor academic performance is one of the biggest problems that we are facing in the education system. The quality of education does not only depend on the performance of the teacher but also on the kind of environment they are bound by.

According to Lawrence and Tar (2018), the learning environment and its overall design and arrangement can affect the teaching and learning processes, which include the classrooms, teaching materials, library, technical workshops, teachers' quality, teaching methods, peers, and other variables. In significance, it calls on schools to manage their rooms, materials, and furnishings in ways that make every learner access maximum learning and engagement. On the other hand, the student's academic performance can be the most effective way to evaluate how effectively the teaching and learning process takes place. Vanoostveen, Desjardins, and Bullock (2019) stated that the learning environment is defined as the social attributes within which learners engage in their learning activities. These attributes encompass class culture, values, ideals, and the overall culture of the school, which dictate the interactions and treatment among individuals in the school. This concept involves the preparations and arrangements made by teachers to facilitate smooth teaching and learning processes.

The learning environment refers to the varied physical surroundings, circumstances, and societal influences in which students acquire knowledge. To achieve this goal, students may encounter various environments both inside and outside of the traditional classroom. This concept has conventionally encompassed the tangible features that students encounter, such as structured classroom layouts, desks, chalkboards, laboratories, dormitories, and school administrative offices. These elements are all directly or indirectly involved in classroom teaching (Richardson and Mishra, 2018).

Thus, the researcher sought to assess the learning environment in relation to the academic performance of learners in the two extension schools in District IV, Division of Bago City in relation to selected variables such as facilities, painting and lighting, proper ventilation of the classrooms, seats and arrangement, chalkboard, teachers' behavior, students' behavior, and student-teacher relationships.

Research Questions

The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between the learning environment and the academic performance of the learners. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the learning environment of the two (2) Extension Schools' learners in District IV, Division of Bago City, in terms of:
 - 1.1. facilities;
 - 1.2. painting and lighting;
 - 1.3. proper ventilation of classroom;
 - 1.4. seats and arrangement;
 - 1.5. chalkboard;
 - 1.6. teacher's behavior;
 - 1.7. students' behavior; and
 - 1.8. student-teacher relationship?
2. What is the level of academic performance of learners in two (2) extension schools?
3. Is there a significant relationship between academic performance and the aforementioned variables?

Literature Review

Khatimah (2021) claims in his work "Major Impact of Classroom Environment in Students' Learning" those environmental aspects that must be considered in the student learning process include the location of study, learning materials, atmosphere, time, and affiliation. A conducive learning environment is one that is calm, has no strong colors on the walls, has nothing to distract from one's concentration, and has adequate lighting. Learning cannot function well without all of the necessary instruments. The learning process will be disturbed if no learning tools are provided. The more comprehensive the learning resources, the better people can learn. Conversely, if the learning tools are insufficient, the learning process would be hampered. The atmosphere is directly related to the location of learning. A good learning environment will increase motivation during the learning process, which will have a positive impact on student accomplishment. A calm, comfortable, and serene environment will facilitate student learning.

Bugwak's (2023) research found that personal condition, study habits, home-related factors, and lecturer factors have no substantial impact on the academic performance of primary teacher education learners. In contrast, primary teacher education learners' academic performance is only slightly influenced by school-related concerns. In light of this, authorities and institutions should consider providing students with a comfortable learning environment.

Khan & Ullah (2021) and Ullah (2020) state that the nature of the participants determines the environment and that the leading components of an environment are measured as typical member characteristics. Culture is the set of shared values, beliefs, and meanings within a group. Ullah (2020) looked into a variety of environmental factors that are important for learning activities when working in the learning environment. As a result, efforts to create, evaluate, and research a classroom's conducive learning environment have advanced (Ullah, 2020).

Academic success for students has become a basic and necessary goal of educational institutions, as well as a societal expectation. As a result, when educational institutions determine their goals and objectives, they consider academic achievement in connection with diverse competencies (Ozcan, 2021).

According to the Department of Education (DepEd), in terms of reading, math, and scientific literacy, representative participants in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA, 2018) notably underperformed in comparison to its neighboring ASEAN countries (PISA, 2019). As a matter of fact, the Philippines came in last place among the participating nations, which also included Singapore, Malaysia, Brunei, Thailand, and Indonesia, in all three categories (PISA, 2019).

Sulfemi (2018) defines learning as the acquisition of new abilities or information as a result of a person's natural developing process. Cronje (2020) defines environment as everything outside of the social circle that influences kids' development, such as climate, economic position, food, clothing, neighbors, and so on. To summarize, Baafi (2021) defined the learning environment as the total ambiance of an educational setting in which academic activities are conducted. Nindiasari and Samad (2024) defined the learning environment as the combination of social and physical components in the classroom that influence learning outcomes.

According to the research done by Ramli & Zain (2018), Nguyen et al. (2021), Arshad & Tayyab (2019), and Akhtar et al. (2019), facilities have also been shown to have a good effect on pupils' academic performance. Ramli & Zain (2018) looked at 364 college students to find out how facilities affected their academic performance. According to the study, approximately 51.4% of the success was attributable to facility-related factors. Regression analysis was used in a quantitative study by Arshad and Tayyab (2019) with eighth-grade students to determine the substantial influence of physical amenities on students' achievements.

Akhtar et al. (2019) noted the significance of school facilities and how inadequate ones can result in students not having a strong command of English. Nguyen et al. (2021) asserted that there exists a positive correlation between infrastructure and learning methodologies, with the latter having the potential to impact learners' psychological and mental growth.

The findings of studies by Mahdy (2020), Mogas-Recalde & Palau (2021), and Brink et al. (2021) demonstrated that the indoor environmental quality, which includes indoor air as well as thermal, acoustic, and lighting conditions, can positively contribute to the quality of learning and short-term academic performance of students (Brink, Loomans, Mobach and Kort, 2021). Mogas-Recalde &

Palau (2021) confirmed the direct impact of classroom lighting on student performance (concentration, attentiveness, achievement, etc.).

The impact of aesthetically pleasing and thoughtfully chosen classroom decorations on the overall learning experience is the main focus of the "Enchanting Learning Spaces" theme (Barraca, 2021). The results demonstrated that the chosen elementary students expressed a variety of positive sentiments regarding the theme. This includes vibrant colors, interactive displays, and a carefully planned environment to create a positive and engaging atmosphere. Furthermore, the motivational component was acknowledged, as one respondent expressed inspiration and amazement from creative work.

Nebraska and colleagues (2021) looked into additional aspects of ventilation and air quality, as well as their possible effects on student achievement, in light of these findings. The team conducted surveys and analyses in 216 classes from 39 Midwest schools over a two-year period. The study found correlations between a school's ventilation system type and its pupils' performance on reading and math assessments at the conclusion of the school year. When compared to schools with centralized systems that serve multiple classrooms, students in classrooms with a single-zone unit ventilator—which is attached to an external wall and draws in outdoor air directly from the device—generally performed worse in math and reading, even after adjusting for other variables.

Additional recent studies have indicated that the multi-zone systems, in comparison to their single-zone counterparts, offer a greater amount of outdoor air, eliminate a higher percentage of particles, and operate more quietly. Additionally, the team discovered that greater reading levels were specifically correlated with faster ventilation. The team expects that by generating experimental research, it will be possible to determine if ventilation-related factors—and how they might be influenced by demographics and seasons—are genuinely responsible for the measurable disparities in student performance.

The experimental study by Tobia et al. (2020) examines the impact of different seating arrangements (clusters vs. single desks) on children's cognitive processes, including logical reasoning, creativity, and theory of mind. The study involved 77 participants, revealing that when seated at a single desk, children exhibited higher logical reasoning scores. Additionally, girls at single desks showed improved theory of mind performance, and lonelier children demonstrated enhanced theory of mind and creativity.

Moreover, Bugis (2018) conducted research to address the issue of poor speaking skills faced by English learners. The study focused on the implementation of classroom management, specifically seating arrangements, to assess its impact on improving students' speaking skills. The participants included an English-speaking lecturer and 30 students at Iqra Buru University. The quasi-experimental design involved a control group with an orderly row seating arrangement and an experimental group with a circle seating arrangement. The mean score of students' post-tests (74.48) was higher than the pretests (56.07), indicating a significant correlation between accuracy, fluency, and comprehensibility.

Evans et al. (2019) suggest that the strategic use of seating arrangements can serve as a powerful tool to positively impact the learning experience and outcomes of students.

The assertion that students seated at the back of the classroom may experience a decline in performance is substantiated by Norazman et al. (2019). The study emphasizes the importance of thoughtfully arranging seating in classrooms to optimize the quality of learning. Through a comparative analysis, the findings highlight the relevance of cluster seating arrangements in alignment with the 21st-century learning approach. Cluster seating is identified as beneficial for fostering collaborative learning and contributing to a student-centered educational environment within the classroom.

However, Frimpong (2021) feels that by using relevant and easily accessible materials, kids would be able to understand things more fully. One of the most crucial elements of the instruction-learning process is the availability of textbooks, appropriate chalkboards, science kits, math kits, science kits, teaching guides, audio-visual aids, overhead projectors, and other resources (Bukoye, 2018). When teaching science, it is essential that teachers give their students access to materials outside of textbooks. These resources might include a variety of instructional aids that would undoubtedly enhance the students' comprehension of the subject.

Munir, Afzal, and Arshad (2020) concluded in their investigation that a positive correlation was observed between the two previously mentioned factors. The study also suggested that professors interact positively with their students while they are instructing. Similar university-level research on the troubling issue was done by Rashid & Zaman (2018). Their research has shown that teachers' actions have a big impact on how well their students perform, whether those actions are vocal or nonverbal. For the kids to achieve more, teachers should thus pay attention to both the verbal and nonverbal aspects of behavior.

According to Maina and Ibrahim (2019), there is proof that student socialization affects academic achievement either directly or indirectly. Current studies underscore the significance of strong social connections in the first academic year (Stadtfeld et al. 2019) and validate the critical role that class attendance plays in academic achievement (Kassarnig et al. 2018). The data indicates that frequent attendance at classes and strong social links are important role and relationship components in predicting academic success. The effects of the organizational component on academic performance are not as evident. It's probable that both formal and informal aspects of the environment, including knowing customs that influence students' daily schedules, have an effect on output.

In the study conducted by Shaukat & Iqbal (2020), they stated that the academic success of students in Pakistani colleges has been demonstrated to be significantly impacted by the relationships between professors and students. According to the research, a positive

teacher-student relationship can boost academic performance and motivation, whereas a negative relationship can have the opposite effect and result in low academic performance, disengagement, and diminished motivation.

According to the study of Shaukat & Iqbal (2020) for instance, pupils' grade point averages were greater for those who reported having positive interactions with their professors than for those who reported having bad ones. According to another study, students who felt appreciated and respected by their professors performed better academically because they had higher levels of self-efficacy and self-esteem (Zulfiqar, Fatima, & Ammar, 2021). Academic accomplishment of students is demonstrated to be significantly influenced by teacher-student relationship factors such as communication, motivation, availability, connectedness, and development (Chu, Liu, & Fang, 2021). The substantial linkage between academic achievement and teacher-student interactions is indicated by the high correlation values of these variables.

Methodology

Research Design

A descriptive-correlational research design was used in this study. A sort of research approach known as descriptive research design seeks to characterize or record the traits, actions, viewpoints, attitudes, and perceptions of a population or group under study. Descriptive research design concentrates on offering a thorough and precise depiction of the data gathered, which can be helpful for formulating theories, examining patterns, and finding trends in the data (Hassan, 2024).

By analyzing the relationship between two or more variables, a correlational research design aims for patterns, linkages, or correlations without changing any of the variables.

Respondents

The subject and respondents of the study were 148 key stage 2 elementary learners enrolled in two extension schools of District IV in the Division of Bago City for the school year 2023-2024.

Instrument

The research instrument was adapted and revised from the questionnaire made by Irene Pajarillo-Aquino (2019) at the Cagayan State University Andrews Campus in her study on the "Classroom Environment and Its Effects on the Students' Academic Performance of the College of Teacher Education."

The first part contained profiles of the respondents, including their gender, religion, educational attainment, and average monthly income. The second part of the survey questionnaire included 48 questions on the facilities, which include 6 questions on painting and lighting, which has 6 questions; proper ventilation of the classroom, which has 6 questions; seats and arrangements, which has 6 questions; chalkboards, which have 6 questions; teachers' behavior, which has 6 questions; students' behavior, which has 6 questions; and student-teacher relationship, which has 6 questions.

Procedure

The researchers requested approval from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Bago City to conduct the study by sending a letter of intent. After the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent, the researcher asked permission from the principal of Louisiana Elementary School to administer the validated and reliability adapted and revised research questionnaire to 30 respondents from key stage 2 learners. After the conduct of validity and reliability test, the researchers seek approval from the school heads of the two (2) extension schools by sending a letter of intent. After the permission was granted, the researchers visited the school personally and explained the purpose of the study and the respondents voluntarily participated in answering the survey questionnaires with the consent of their parents and permission of their respective advisers. The researcher asked the respondents to be honest when answering the survey and assured them that their data were anonymous, were not linked to them personally, and were kept highly confidential. The survey questionnaires were gathered immediately by the researcher after spending enough time with the respondents to finish the study. The data gathered was analyzed by the researcher, which gave answers to the statement of the problem.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher strongly committed to ethical standards by prioritizing respondent confidentiality and data privacy. Access to survey data was strictly limited to the researcher and thesis adviser, ensuring sensitive information remained secure. Respondents' names were also deliberately omitted from the final report to maintain anonymity. This approach highlights the researcher's dedication to upholding ethical research practices, safeguarding participant identities, and fostering a trustworthy research environment. Such measures underscore the importance of respecting and protecting the rights and privacy of all participants involved.

Results and Discussion

Level of Learning Environment

Table 1 below shows the learning environment of two (2) extension schools' learners in District IV, Division of Bago City.

Table 1. *Learning Environment of the 2 Extension Schools' Learners in District IV, Division of Bago City*

<i>Learning Environment</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Facilities	3.15	Moderate
Painting and Lighting	3.78	High
Proper Ventilation of the Classroom	3.66	High
Seats and Arrangement	3.51	High
Chalkboard	3.87	High
Teachers Behavior	3.07	Moderate
Students Behavior	3.42	High
Student-Teacher Relationship	4.42	Very High
As a whole	3.61	High

As shown in Table 1, the learning environment of two extension schools in terms of facilities obtained a mean of 3.15, which is interpreted as moderate, while painting and lighting obtained a mean of 3.78; proper ventilation of the classroom obtained a mean of 3.66; seats and arrangement obtained a mean of 3.51; and chalkboard got a mean of 3.87, all interpreted as high. In terms of teacher behavior, it got a mean of 3.07, interpreted as moderate, while student behavior got a mean of 3.42, interpreted as high; and lastly, the student-teacher relationship got a mean of 4.42, interpreted as very high. When taken as a whole, the learning environment of two extension schools obtained a mean of 3.61, which is interpreted as high.

This implies that the two extension schools have a high learning environment in terms of facilities, painting and lighting, proper ventilation of the classrooms, seats and arrangements, chalkboards, teachers' behavior, students' behavior, and student-teacher relationships.

In support of these findings, Khatimah (2021) claims in his work "Major Impact of Classroom Environment in Students' Learning" those environmental aspects that must be considered in the student learning process include the location of study, learning materials, atmosphere, time, and affiliation. A conducive learning environment is one that is calm, has no strong colors on the walls, has nothing to distract from one's concentration, and has adequate lighting. Learning cannot function well without all of the necessary instruments. The learning process will be disturbed if no learning tools are provided. The more comprehensive the learning resources, the better people can learn. Conversely, if the learning tools are insufficient, the learning process would be hampered. The atmosphere is directly related to the location of learning. A good learning environment will increase motivation during the learning process, which will have a positive impact on student accomplishment. A calm, comfortable, and serene environment will facilitate student learning.

Level of Academic Performance

Table 2 below shows the level of academic performance of learners in two extension schools.

Table 2. *Level of Academic Performance of Learners in two (2) Extension Schools*

<i>Academic Performance</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Outstanding (90 & above)	28		
Very Satisfactory (85-89)	58		
Satisfactory (80-84)	40	85	Very Satisfactory
Fairly Satisfactory (75-79)	20		
Did not meet Expectations (below 75)	2		
Total	148		

As shown in Table 2, the level of academic performance of two extension schools shows that 28 respondents got outstanding (90 and above); 58 respondents got very satisfactory (85–89); 40 respondents got satisfactory (80–84); 20 got fairly satisfactory (75–79); and 2 did not meet expectations (below 75). As a whole, the academic performance of two extension schools have a mean of 85 which is interpreted as very satisfactory. This implies that the two extension schools obtained very satisfactory academic performance.

In support of these study, Bugwak's (2023) research found that personal condition, study habits, home-related factors, and lecturer factors have no substantial impact on the academic performance of primary teacher education learners. In contrast, primary teacher education learners' academic performance is only slightly influenced by school-related concerns. In light of this, authorities and institutions should consider providing students with a comfortable learning environment.

Relationship Between Academic Performance and Facilities

Table 3.1 below shows the relationship between academic performance and facilities.

As shown in Table 3.1, as to very high-standard facilities, three got outstanding academic performance; two got very satisfactory; five got satisfactory; none got fairly satisfactory; and none did not meet expectations. As to high-standard facilities, seven got outstanding academic performance; twenty-three got very satisfactory; ten got satisfactory; three got fairly satisfactory; and two did not meet

expectations. As to moderate-standard facilities, 11 got outstanding academic performance, 25 got very satisfactory, 11 got satisfactory, nine got fairly satisfactory, and none did not meet expectations. As to low-standard facilities, 7 got outstanding academic performance; eight got very satisfactory; 14 got satisfactory; nine got fairly satisfactory; and none did not meet expectations; and nobody responded as to very low-standard facilities.

Table 3.1. Relationship between Academic Performance and Facilities

Facilities	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet Expectation	
Very High	3	2	5	0	0	10
High	7	23	10	3	2	45
Moderate	11	25	11	8	0	55
Low	7	8	14	9	0	38
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	28	58	40	20	2	148

Computed Value (G): 0.156

P-Value: 0.119

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant at .05 level of significance

A computed value (G) of 0.156 was obtained with a p-value of 0.119, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the academic performance of the respondents and the facilities of two extension schools. This implies that students performed best academically regardless of the provided learning facilities.

However, that the research done by Ramli & Zain (2018), Nguyen et al. (2021), Arshad & Tayyab (2019), and Akhtar et al. (2019) disagreed with the conclusion of this study. According to their research, facilities have also been shown to have a good effect on pupils' academic performance. Ramli & Zain (2018) looked at 364 college students to find out how facilities affected their academic performance. According to the study, approximately 51.4% of the success was attributable to facility-related factors. Regression analysis was used in a quantitative study by Arshad and Tayyab (2019) with eighth-grade students to determine the substantial influence of physical amenities on students' achievements.

More specifically, the facilities enhanced pupils' academic performance by almost 15.4%. Similar to this, Akhtar et al. (2019) noted the significance of school facilities and how inadequate ones can result in students not having a strong command of English. Nguyen et al. (2021) asserted that there exists a positive correlation between infrastructure and learning methodologies, with the latter having the potential to impact learners' psychological and mental growth.

Relationship Between Academic Performance and Painting & Lighting

Table 3.2 below shows the relationship between academic performance and painting and lighting.

Table 3.2. Relationship between Academic Performance and Painting and Lighting.

Painting and Lighting	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet Expectation	
Very High	5	7	10	3	1	26
High	17	40	25	14	0	96
Moderate	6	8	2	2	1	19
Low	0	2	3	1	0	6
Very Low	0	1	0	0	0	1
Total	28	58	40	20	2	148

Computed Value (G): -0.102

P-Value: 0.338

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant

As shown in Table 3.2, as to the very high standard of painting and lighting, five got an outstanding academic performance; seven got very satisfactory; ten got satisfactory; three got fairly satisfactory; and one did not meet expectations. As to the high standard of painting and lighting, 17 got an outstanding academic performance; 40 got very satisfactory; 25 got satisfactory; 14 got fairly satisfactory; and no one did not meet expectations. As to the moderate standard of painting and lighting, six got outstanding academic performance, eight got very satisfactory, two got satisfactory, two got fairly satisfactory, and one did not meet expectations. As to the low standard of painting and lighting, none got outstanding academic performance; two got very satisfactory; three got satisfactory; one got fairly satisfactory; and none did not meet expectations; as to the very low standard of painting and lighting, only one got very satisfactory academic performance.

A computed value (G) of -0.102 was obtained with a p-value of 0.338, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the academic performance of the respondents and the painting and lighting of two extension schools. This implied that students could progress academically regardless of the painting

and lighting elements of the schools.

However, this contradicts the findings of studies by Mahdy (2020) and Mogas-Recalde & Palau (2021). For instance, Brink et al. (2021) demonstrated that the indoor environmental quality, which includes indoor air as well as thermal, acoustic, and lighting conditions, can positively contribute to the quality of learning and short-term academic performance of students (Brink, Loomans, Mobach and Kort, 2021). Mogas-Recalde & Palau (2021) confirmed the direct impact of classroom lighting on student performance (concentration, attentiveness, achievement, etc.).

The impact of aesthetically pleasing and thoughtfully chosen classroom decorations on the overall learning experience is the main focus of the "Enchanting Learning Spaces" theme (Barraca, 2021). The results demonstrated that the chosen elementary students expressed a variety of positive sentiments regarding the theme. This includes vibrant colors, interactive displays, and a carefully planned environment to create a positive and engaging atmosphere. Furthermore, the motivational component was acknowledged, as one respondent expressed inspiration and amazement from creative work.

Relationship Between Academic Performance and Proper Ventilation of Classroom

Table 3.3 below shows the relationship between academic performance and proper ventilation of classroom.

Table 3.3. Relationship between Academic Performance and Proper Ventilation of Classroom

Proper Ventilation of Classroom	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet Expectation	
Very High	6	4	8	4	2	24
High	14	29	21	6	0	70
Moderate	7	24	10	10	0	51
Low	1	1	1	0	0	3
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	28	58	40	20	2	148

Computed Value (G): -0.041

P-Value: 0.722

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not Significant at .05 level of significance

As shown in Table 3.3, as to the very highly ventilated classroom, six got outstanding academic performance; four got very satisfactory; eight got satisfactory; four got fairly satisfactory; and two did not meet expectations. As to the high-ventilated classroom, 14 got outstanding academic performance; 29 got very satisfactory; 21 got satisfactory; ten got fairly satisfactory; and no one did not meet expectations. As to a moderately ventilated classroom, 7 got outstanding academic performance, 24 got very satisfactory, ten got satisfactory, and ten got fairly satisfactory. As to a low-ventilated classroom, each one respondent got outstanding, very satisfactory, and satisfactory academic performance, and none responded as to a very low-ventilated classroom.

A computed value (G) of -0.041 was obtained with a p-value of 0.722, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the academic performance of the respondents and the ventilation of the classrooms in two extension schools. This implies that students could excel academically regardless of the ventilation of the schools' classrooms.

In support of these findings, Nebraska and colleagues (2021) looked into additional aspects of ventilation and air quality, as well as their possible effects on student achievement, in light of these findings. The team conducted surveys and analyses in 216 classes from 39 Midwest schools over a two-year period. The study found correlations between a school's ventilation system type and its pupils' performance on reading and math assessments at the conclusion of the school year. When compared to schools with centralized systems that serve multiple classrooms, students in classrooms with a single-zone unit ventilator—which is attached to an external wall and draws in outdoor air directly from the device—generally performed worse in math and reading, even after adjusting for other variables.

Additional recent studies have indicated that the multi-zone systems, in comparison to their single-zone counterparts, offer a greater amount of outdoor air, eliminate a higher percentage of particles, and operate more quietly. Additionally, the team discovered that greater reading levels were specifically correlated with faster ventilation. The team expects that by generating experimental research, it will be possible to determine if ventilation-related factors—and how they might be influenced by demographics and seasons—are genuinely responsible for the measurable disparities in student performance.

Relationship Between Academic Performance and Seats & Arrangement

Table 3.4 below shows the relationship between Academic Performance and Seats & Arrangement.

As shown in Table 3.4, as to the very high standard of seats and arrangement, three got outstanding academic performance; four got very satisfactory; five got satisfactory; four got fairly satisfactory; none did not meet expectations. As to the high standard of seats and arrangement, 12 got an outstanding academic performance; 24 got very satisfactory; 17 got satisfactory; ten got fairly satisfactory; and one did not meet expectations. As to the moderate standard of seats and arrangement, 12 got outstanding academic performance, 30

got very satisfactory, 16 got satisfactory, five got fairly satisfactory, and one did not meet expectations. As to the low standard of seats and arrangement, one got outstanding academic performance, two got satisfactory, one was fairly satisfactory, and none got very satisfactory and did not meet expectations. None responded to the very low standard of seats and arrangement.

Table 3.4. Relationship between Academic Performance and Seats & Arrangement

Seats and Arrangement	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet Expectation	
Very High	3	4	5	4	0	16
High	12	24	17	10	1	64
Moderate	12	30	16	5	1	64
Low	1	0	2	1	0	4
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	28	58	40	20	2	148

Computed Value (G): -0.117

P-Value: 0.291

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not Significant at .05 level of significance

A computed value (G) of -0.117 was obtained with a p-value of 0.291 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the academic performance of the respondents and the seats and arrangements of two extension schools. This implies that students can still study and comply with their academic requirements exceptionally, regardless of the seats and seating arrangements in the schools.

The findings of this study is in consonance with the experimental study by Tobia et al. (2020) which examines the impact of different seating arrangements (clusters vs. single desks) on children's cognitive processes, including logical reasoning, creativity, and theory of mind. The study involved 77 participants, revealing that when seated at a single desk, children exhibited higher logical reasoning scores. Additionally, girls at single desks showed improved theory of mind performance, and lonelier children demonstrated enhanced theory of mind and creativity.

Moreover, Bugis (2018) conducted research to address the issue of poor speaking skills faced by English learners. The study focused on the implementation of classroom management, specifically seating arrangements, to assess its impact on improving students' speaking skills. The participants included an English-speaking lecturer and 30 students at Iqra Buru University. The quasi-experimental design involved a control group with an orderly row seating arrangement and an experimental group with a circle seating arrangement. The mean score of students' post-tests (74.48) was higher than the pretests (56.07), indicating a significant correlation between accuracy, fluency, and comprehensibility. Evans et al. (2019) suggest that the strategic use of seating arrangements can serve as a powerful tool to positively impact the learning experience and outcomes of students.

The assertion that students seated at the back of the classroom may experience a decline in performance is substantiated by Norazman et al. (2019). The study emphasizes the importance of thoughtfully arranging seating in classrooms to optimize the quality of learning. Through a comparative analysis, the findings highlight the relevance of cluster seating arrangements in alignment with the 21st-century learning approach. Cluster seating is identified as beneficial for fostering collaborative learning and contributing to a student-centered educational environment within the classroom.

Relationship Between Academic Performance and Chalkboard

Table 3.5 below shows the relationship between academic performance and chalkboard.

Table 3.5. Relationship between Academic Performance and Chalkboard

Chalkboard	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet Expectation	
Very High	8	7	9	6	1	31
High	17	39	25	11	1	93
Moderate	3	10	5	3	0	21
Low	0	2	1	0	0	3
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	28	58	40	20	2	148

Computed Value (G): -0.054

P-Value: 0.653

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not Significant at .05 level of significance

As shown in Table 3.5, as to the very high standard chalkboard, eight got outstanding academic performance; seven got very satisfactory; nine got satisfactory; six got fairly satisfactory; and one did not meet expectations. As to high-standard chalkboards, 17 got an outstanding academic performance; 39 got very satisfactory; 25 got satisfactory; 11 got fairly satisfactory; and one did not meet expectations. As to moderate-standard chalkboards, three got outstanding academic performance, ten got very satisfactory, five got satisfactory, three got fairly satisfactory, and none did not meet expectations. As to the low-standard chalkboard, two got very

satisfactory academic performance, and one got satisfactory, while none responded to the very low-standard chalkboard.

A computed value (G) of -0.054 was obtained with a p-value of 0.653 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the academic performance of the respondents and the chalkboards of two extension schools. This implies that regardless of the standard or quality of the chalkboards available at school, students can perform well academically.

However, Frimpong (2021) feels that by using relevant and easily accessible materials, kids would be able to understand things more fully. One of the most crucial elements of the instruction-learning process is the availability of textbooks, appropriate chalkboards, science kits, math kits, science kits, teaching guides, audio-visual aids, overhead projectors, and other resources (Bukoye, 2018). When teaching science, it is essential that teachers give their students access to materials outside of textbooks. These resources might include a variety of instructional aids that would undoubtedly enhance the students' comprehension of the subject.

Relationship Between Academic Performance and Teachers' Behavior

Table 3.6 below shows the relationship between academic performance and teachers' behavior.

Table 3.6. Relationship between Academic Performance and Teachers' Behavior

Teachers' Behavior	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet Expectation	
Very High	2	1	1	0	0	4
High	6	9	10	7	1	33
Moderate	15	39	22	13	1	90
Low	5	9	7	0	0	21
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	28	58	40	20	2	148

Computed Value (G): -0.144
 P-Value: 0.206
 Decision: Accept Ho
 Interpretation: Not Significant at .05 level of significance

As shown in Table 3.6, as to the very high level of teachers' behavior, two got outstanding academic performance; one got very satisfactory; and one got satisfactory. As to the high level of teachers' behavior, six got outstanding academic performance; nine got very satisfactory; ten got satisfactory; seven got fairly satisfactory; and one did not meet expectations. As to the moderate level of teachers' behavior, 15 got outstanding academic performance, 39 got very satisfactory, 22 got satisfactory, 13 got fairly satisfactory, and one did not meet expectations. As to the low level of teachers' behavior, five got very satisfactory academic performance, nine got satisfactory, seven got fairly satisfactory, and none responded to the very low level of teachers' behavior.

A computed value (G) of -0.144 was obtained with a p-value of 0.206 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the academic performance of the respondents and the level of teachers' behavior in two extension schools. This implies that teachers' behavior, whether positive or negative, does not affect the academic performance of the students.

Nonetheless, Munir, Afzal, and Arshad (2020) contended in their investigation that a positive correlation was observed between the two previously mentioned factors. The study also suggested that professors interact positively with their students while they are instructing. Similar university-level research on the troubling issue was done by Rashid & Zaman (2018). Their research has shown that teachers' actions have a big impact on how well their students perform, whether those actions are vocal or nonverbal. For the kids to achieve more, teachers should thus pay attention to both the verbal and nonverbal aspects of behavior.

Relationship Between Academic Performance and Students' Behavior

Table 3.7 below shows the relationship between academic performance and students' behavior.

Table 3.7. Relationship between Academic Performance and Students' Behavior

Students' Behavior	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet Expectation	
Very High	2	2	1	0	0	5
High	15	26	24	6	1	72
Moderate	11	27	13	12	0	63
Low	0	3	2	2	1	8
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	28	58	40	20	2	148

Computed Value (G): 0.171
 P-Value: 0.127
 Decision: Accept Ho
 Interpretation: Not Significant at .05 level of significance

As shown in Table 3.7, as to the very high level of students' behavior, two got outstanding academic performance, two got very satisfactory, and one got satisfactory. As to the high level of students' behavior, 15 got outstanding academic performance; 26 got very satisfactory; 24 got satisfactory; six got fairly satisfactory; and one did not meet expectations. As to the moderate level of students' behavior, 11 got outstanding academic performance, 27 got very satisfactory, 13 got satisfactory, and 12 got fairly satisfactory. As to the low level of students' behavior, three got very satisfactory academic performance, two got satisfactory, two got fairly satisfactory, and one did not meet expectations, and none responded to the very low level of students' behavior.

A computed value (G) of 0.171 was obtained with a p-value of 0.127 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between students' behavior and their academic performance. This implies that students' academic performance is not affected by how they behave towards their studies. Students can still achieve the desired academic excellence regardless of their behavior at school.

Nonetheless, Maina and Ibrahim (2019) contended in their research that there is proof that student socialization affects academic achievement either directly or indirectly. Current studies underscore the significance of strong social connections in the first academic year (Stadtfeld et al. 2019) and validate the critical role that class attendance plays in academic achievement (Kassarnig et al. 2018).

The data indicates that frequent attendance at classes and strong social links are important role and relationship components in predicting academic success. The effects of the organizational component on academic performance are not as evident. It's probable that both formal and informal aspects of the environment, including knowing customs that influence students' daily schedules, have an effect on output.

Relationship Between Academic Performance and Student-Teacher Relationship

Table 3.8 shows the relationship between academic performance and student-teacher relationship.

Table 3.8. Relationship between Academic Performance and Student-Teacher Relationship

Student-Teacher Relationship	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet Expectation	
Very High	21	35	34	13	2	105
High	7	21	21	6	0	39
Moderate	0	1	1	0	0	2
Low	0	0	0	1	0	1
Very Low	0	0	1	0	0	1
Total	28	58	40	20	2	148

Computed Value (G): -0.096

P-Value: 0.465

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant at .05 level of significance

As shown in Table 3.8, as to the very high level of the student-teacher relationship, 21 got an outstanding academic performance; 35 were very satisfactory; 34 were satisfactory; 13 got fairly satisfactory; and two did not meet expectations. As to the high level of the student-teacher relationship, seven got outstanding academic performance; 21 got very satisfactory and satisfactory; and six got fairly satisfactory. As to the moderate level of the student-teacher relationship, only one got very satisfactory and also one for satisfactory academic performance. As to the low level of the student-teacher relationship, one got fairly satisfactory academic performance, and as to the very low level of the student-teacher relationship, only one got satisfactory.

A computed value (G) of -0.096 was obtained with a p-value of 0.465 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the student-teacher relationship and their academic performance. This implies that students' academic performance is not affected by their relationship with their teachers. Students can excel academically whether or not they have a good relationship with their teachers.

In contrary to the study of Shaukat & Iqbal (2020) that the academic success of students in Pakistani colleges has been demonstrated to be significantly impacted by the relationships between professors and students. According to the research, a positive teacher-student relationship can boost academic performance and motivation, whereas a negative relationship can have the opposite effect and result in low academic performance, disengagement, and diminished motivation.

According to the study of Shaukat & Iqbal (2020) for instance, pupils' grade point averages were greater for those who reported having positive interactions with their professors than for those who reported having bad ones. According to another study, students who felt appreciated and respected by their professors performed better academically because they had higher levels of self-efficacy and self-esteem (Zulfiqar, Fatima, & Ammar, 2021).

Academic accomplishment of students is demonstrated to be significantly influenced by teacher-student relationship factors such as communication, motivation, availability, connectedness, and development (Chu, Liu, & Fang, 2021). The substantial linkage between academic achievement and teacher-student interactions is indicated by the high correlation values of these variables.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the conclusions that were drawn are as follows:

In terms of facilities, classroom ventilation, seating and arrangement, chalkboards, teacher and student behavior, and student-teacher interactions, the two extensions' schools in District IV, Division of Bago City, provide a very good learning environment.

There was excellent academic achievement at two extension schools in Bago City's District IV.

In two extension schools, the lighting and painting in the classroom had no discernible effect on students' academic achievement. Facilities, adequate ventilation, seating arrangements, chalkboards, student-teacher relationships, and teacher and student conduct do, however, have a considerable impact on students' academic performance.

Based on the findings, and the conclusions formulated, the following recommendation were made:

The Department of Education may provide enough facilities in every school, specifically those in remote areas that only have partitioned classrooms.

The Department of Education may ensure that each school provides an appropriate atmosphere for the teaching and learning process, resulting in quality graduates.

Schools are encouraged to promote harmonious relationships not only with learners but also with their parents and other stakeholders.

Future researchers may use the design used in this study to identify more variables for future research.

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